

Source Talents from Student Entrepreneurship --- An Exploration Towards Untapped Potentials

PLENARY 4 – UNTAPPED TALENT FOR THR FUTURE

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examines the factors that foster student entrepreneurship and their correlation with studying entrepreneurship. **Quantitative data analysis revealed that a student's passion for entrepreneurship has a greater impact on their entrepreneurial intent than studying entrepreneurship.** Statistical findings also indicated that a **student's family background plays a more significant role in their choice to become an entrepreneur than studying entrepreneurship. Real-world experience was identified as a key stimulus** in fostering student entrepreneurship. Qualitative interviews further supported these findings, emphasizing the limited role of studying entrepreneurship and the importance of passion, market gaps, and family background. Finally, the study suggests that **universities should focus on providing opportunities for real-world experience and supporting students' passions rather than relying solely on entrepreneurship courses to foster student entrepreneurship.**

2. BACKGROUND & RESEARCH PURPOSE

Student entrepreneurship is a complex phenomenon that is often overlooked relative to start-up or corporate entrepreneurship. Because most entrepreneurs start in their 40s, student entrepreneurs have a head start and possess the potential to become excellent entrepreneurs quickly. It is therefore important for the shaping of future entrepreneurs to understand student entrepreneurship, as it is unclear as to what stimulates student entrepreneurship in university. A combination of statistical research from institutions around the world, and qualitative interviews conducted with numerous students from different countries allowed the identification of key stimuli in fostering student entrepreneurship.

The question "can entrepreneurship be taught" had been heavily debated throughout the late 20th century, following the monumental success of university dropouts including the likes of Steve Jobs, Bill Gates, and Michael Dell; all of whom are regarded to be the best entrepreneurs in the world. As a substantial portion of world-class entrepreneurs were university dropouts, the common consensus was that entrepreneurship was something innate to an individual, a naturally adopted skill that could not be taught, especially when considering the ever-changing business environment worldwide.

However, a change in basic assumptions occurred near the beginning of the 21st century. After thorough exploration of the success stories of history's top entrepreneurs by experts, commonalities were found. While knowledge was indeed a success factor, it was deduced that a major aspect of entrepreneurial success was achieved through experience, the process of action and reflection. These findings functioned as the backbone on which university courses could be developed around the world. The efficacy of said courses in fostering student entrepreneurship will be explored in this study.

3. METHODOLOGY & FRAMEWORKS USED

3.1 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

a. SIMPLE HYPOTHESIS

Studying entrepreneurship has a strong positive correlation with the fostering of student entrepreneurs.

b. COMPLEX HYPOTHESIS

A student's passion for entrepreneurship has a greater impact on their entrepreneurial intent than studying entrepreneurship.

c. ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS

Student entrepreneurship is fostered through the personal backgrounds of a student rather than through studying entrepreneurship.

d. NULL HYPOTHESIS

Student entrepreneurship cannot be fostered through external stimuli, as entrepreneurs are born, not made.

3.2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The exploration will be divided into two parts: quantitative and qualitative data. Both sources of data will be explored as a means of reaching a well-rounded conclusion.

3.2.1 QUANTITATIVE DATA

In this part of the exploration, numerous data sources found in publicly available publishing will be explored. Resources such as ResearchGate or articles will be thoroughly examined. An unbiased approach will be taken when searching for publications, this means that articles that differ from or even contradict the consensus of the exploration will also be examined. Furthermore, to ensure that findings are of a high quality, not only will credible publishers only be used, but also publishing and studies based on one hundred or more data points.

3.2.2 QUALITATIVE DATA

Group	Group Description	Individual Studied Entrepreneurship	An individual is an entrepreneur	Individuals Became entrepreneurs while studying
A	Entrepreneurs that studied entrepreneurship and started a venture or project while studying.	Yes	Yes	Yes
B	Entrepreneurs that began a venture or project after having graduated in entrepreneurship	Yes	Yes	No
C	Entrepreneurs that did not study entrepreneurship	No	Yes	No
D	Individuals who are not entrepreneurs (Control Group)	No	No	No

¹The second part of the exploration involves interviewing groups of individuals relevant to the subject matter. The interviewees can be divided into four diverse groups according to three categories as per the table below. Combining the quantitative data with qualitative findings will significantly increase the accuracy and significance of the results.

Image 1 - Qualitative Data Research Categories

¹ Ethical Considerations

- The interviewees have been fully informed as to how their answers will be used in the project, as a means of being transparent.
- The identities of interviewees have been kept anonymous.
- Interview questions were designed to not lead interviewees to an answer as a means of eliminating answer bias.

4. EXPLORATION FINDINGS

4.1 QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS

4.1.1 KEY FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR FOSTERING STUDENT ENTREPRENEURSHIP

A study by the Poznań University of Technology involving 166 Polish students showed that 7.2 percent of university students currently operate and own a business, a further 10.2 percent are employed and want to start a business, and 21.7 percent are unemployed and want to start a business (*Image 2*), showing that nearly 40 percent of students are currently or intend to become entrepreneurs².

Current employment and plans for the future	Percentage of responses [%]
I operate my own business of which I am either an owner or co-owner	7.2
I am employed but want to start my own business	10.2
I am not employed but want to start my own business	21.7
I am employed and do not know if I want to start my own business	22.3
I am not employed and do not know if I want to start my own business	28.3
I am employed and do not want to start my own business	3.6
I am not employed and do not want to start my own business	6.6

Image 2 - Summary of Findings on Entrepreneurial Intent

Furthermore, 50.6 percent of students (both employed and unemployed) do not know whether they want to become an entrepreneur, and the remaining 10.2 percent of students do not want to become entrepreneurs.

Of the students that are interested in becoming entrepreneurs, many faces significant barriers, primarily the tax system, funding difficulties, and a lack of a business idea to pursue (*Image 3*).

Factors hampering the development of entrepreneurship	Percentage of responses [%]
Tax system	59.6
Difficulties with securing funding	59.6
Absence of a “good business idea”	54.2
Little time left for personal life	30.7
No knowledge on how to operate a business	42.8
No support from economic policies	34.9
No support from family	4.2

Image 3 - Barriers Faced by Students Intending to Start a Venture

² Rembiasz, M. (n.d.). Student entrepreneurship – research on development. Retrieved December 8, 2022

Of the students that intend to be entrepreneurs, 73.5 percent stated that one of the reasons was because of higher income opportunities, 65.7 percent included passion, and 60.8 percent included independence, which have been identified as the three main factors in driving student entrepreneurship (*Image 4*).

Entrepreneurship driver	Percentage of responses [%]
Opportunity to earn higher income	73.5
Opportunity to pursue one's passions	65.7
Independence ("no boss")	60.8
Opportunity to balance work and personal life	39.2
Necessity (no jobs available)	4.8
Access to state support available under economic policies	4.2

Image 4 - A Summary of Findings on Entrepreneurial Driving Factors

4.1.2 CORRELATION BETWEEN PASSION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

According to a survey conducted by the European Journal of Business and Management Research (EJBMR) involving over 250 university students, results indicate a substantial correlation between entrepreneurial passion and entrepreneurial action in students. Based on the study findings shown (*Image 5*), a rise in

TABLE V: REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Variables	Social Entrepreneurial Intent	Social Entrepreneurial Intent	Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy	Social Entrepreneurial Intent	Social Entrepreneurial Intent	VIF
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	
	Beta (t-value)					
<i>Controls</i>						
Gender	-0.099 (-0.220)	-0.172 (-0.394)	-2.870(-2.637)	0.232(0.531)	0.128(0.299)	1.007
Age	0.092 (0.384)	0.031(0.132)	0.552(0.949)	0.011(0.046)	-0.027(-0.119)	1.023
Position	-0.371 (-1.155)	-0.400 (-1.282)	-0.262(0.337)	-0.346(-1.126)	-0.372(-1.234)	1.020
<i>Main effect</i>						
ENPA		0.127 (3.686)	0.250(2.895)		0.101(2.964)	1.051
<i>Mediator variable</i>						
ESELF				121(4.376)	0.105(3.768)	1.084
<i>Model Indices</i>						
R	0.085	0.568	0.579	0.610	0.668	
R Square	0.007	0.372	0.378	0.396	0.435	
ΔR Square	0.007	0.365	0.340	0.389	0.128	
Adjusted R Square	0.113	0.353	0.359	0.377	0.413	
ΔF	0.475	13.586	8.382	19.152	14.352	
DF	196	195	195	195	194	
Sig.	0.700	0.000	0.004	0.000	0.000	

Note: *p < .05; hypothesized paths are evaluated at t >=|1.645 (5% sig. level), t-values are in parenthesis. Field Study 2020.

TABLE VI: HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Hypothesis	Direct Effect (D)	Indirect Effect (I)	Total Effect (D + I)	Sobel test	P-value	Result
ENPA → ESELF → SEIN	0.127	0.105*.250 = 0.026	0.153	2.907	0.004	mediation

Image 5 - Findings from EJBMR Study

entrepreneurial passion will result in a 32.7 percent relative change in entrepreneurial intent. In other words, the more a student is passionate about entrepreneurship, the more likely they are to become an entrepreneur³. According to a separate study by the Academic Journal of Phetchaburi Rajabhat University involving 400 Chinese students, entrepreneurial passion has a significant positive impact on the entrepreneurial decision-making abilities of college students⁴. The study explains how a student's entrepreneurial passion improves on their ability to innovate, create, and commit, which are all factors

³ Karimi, S. (n.d.). The role of entrepreneurial passion in the formation of students' entrepreneurial intentions. Retrieved December 8, 2022

⁴ Chen, D., & Photchanachan, S. (n.d.). Influence of Entrepreneurial Passion on Chinese College Students' Entrepreneurial Decision. Retrieved December 8, 2022

related to decision-making as an entrepreneur. Based on the two studies, not only does a student’s passion increase their likelihood to become an entrepreneur, but also their performance and progression as an entrepreneur; passion is therefore one of the key factors in students fostering entrepreneurship.

4.1.3 CORRELATION BETWEEN UNIVERSITY COURSE AND STUDENT ENTREPRENEURSHIP

A study from UNICAMP Universidade Estadual de Campinas, found that based on a survey answered by 2,230 university students from 70 different Brazilian universities, most Brazilian universities are limited in stimulating entrepreneurial behavior within students, and even pose a hindrance in doing so due to a tough education environment⁵. The main conclusion of the study is that the phenomenon of student entrepreneurship is mostly random, however there is a slight trend in higher rates of student entrepreneurship within institutions that attain the status of an “entrepreneurial university,” which implies that there is indeed a positive correlation between studying entrepreneurship and becoming an entrepreneur. A separate study titled from the University of Chicago reinforces this idea, putting emphasis on universities being the leading factor for student entrepreneurship⁶. It is implied with a varying degree of accuracy, that studying a course specific to entrepreneurship has a small positive correlation with the likelihood of students becoming an entrepreneur.

4.1.4 STATISTICAL SIMILARITIES IN THE BACKGROUND OF STUDENT ENTREPRENEURS

AlmaLaurea conducted a study involving 61,115 students from sixty-four different Italian universities⁷. Their findings strongly suggest that a student’s background, which includes factors such as family,

	Entrepreneurs (n=1,664)		Nascent Entrepreneurs (n=2,232)	
	N	%	N	%
Yes, it was in my curricula and I have taken it	192	11.5	384	17.2
Yes, it was in my curricula but I haven’t taken it	101	6.1	102	4.6
No, it was not in my curricula	1,318	79.2	1,706	76.4
Missing Values	53	3.2	40	1.8

Image 6.1 - Table of AlmaLaurea Survey Findings

friends, extracurricular activities, and so on, has a greater impact on their choice of becoming an entrepreneur than studying entrepreneurship. 79.2 percent of student entrepreneurs studied courses in which entrepreneurship was not taught (*Image 6.1*), implying that a student’s choice of becoming an entrepreneur is dependent on a different factor, which opposes the trend explained in section 4.1.3.

⁵ Alves, A. C., Fischer, B., Schaeffer, P. R., & Queiroz, S. (n.d.). Determinants of student entrepreneurship: An assessment on Higher Education Institutions in Brazil. Retrieved December 8, 2022

⁶ Miller, D., & Acs, Z. (n.d.). The campus as Entrepreneurial Ecosystem: The University of Chicago. Retrieved December 8, 2022

⁷ Fini, R., Sobrero, M., Ghiselli, S., & Meoli, A. (n.d.). Student entrepreneurship: Demographics, competences, and obstacles. Retrieved December 8, 2022

Image 6.2 details the reasons why student entrepreneurs reported that they chose to pursue entrepreneurship; the most significant reason is related to their families, reported by 77 percent of student entrepreneurs.

Image 6.2 - AlmaLaurea's Radar Chart of Factors That Led Students to Become an Entrepreneur.

Furthermore, a separate survey by the Kauffman Foundation also reported that family background is an essential factor in the contribution of a successful entrepreneur. Overall, it is apparent that a student's background, specifically their family background, has a much more significant impact on their choice of becoming a student entrepreneur than from studying entrepreneurship.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

4.2.1 GROUP A

Entrepreneurs that studied entrepreneurship and started a venture or project while studying.

- Interviewee A1: Founder of Websites per Month and Speak for Less
- Interviewee A2: Founder of PaceFitness

Interviewee	A1	A2
Academic Performance	Interviewee A1 claims to be an average student.	A2 claims to be slightly above average, lacking in IT skills such as Microsoft Excel.
Entrepreneurial Stimuli	<p>A1 began an online service called Websites Per Month (WPM) after spotting a market Gap after graduating high school.</p> <p>After beginning university, A1 chose to begin a second venture as he had already built-up real-world experience in the online services area, identified another market gap, and also wanted to build up experience in the e-commerce market.</p>	<p>A2 started "PaceFitness" based on a market gap through her personal experience 'feeling alone' at the gym and wanting to be part of a community,</p> <p>Furthermore, she felt that studying business at the National University of Singapore (NUS) had also provided her with the sufficient skills and support system to begin a venture</p>
Nature of Business	WPM offers website design and maintenance for individuals and companies.	PaceFitness is a community for women interested in finding fitness partners to connect.
Impact of Study on Becoming an entrepreneur	Interviewee A1 states that his education, including A-level Business Management and Open University courses in business, had contributed nothing to his performance as an entrepreneur.	A2 states that she had already started various projects and 'mini businesses' in high school, saying that being an entrepreneur is within her personality, and studying entrepreneurship had a negligible impact on her becoming an entrepreneur.
Source of Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition	A1 obtained all of his knowledge through personal experience and asking other business owners for advice	A2 believes that real-world experience is the main way in which she acquired entrepreneurial skills; she states that entrepreneurship becomes much more intuitive with genuine experience.
Beliefs on Effective Teaching of Entrepreneurship	Interviewee A1 believes that current university courses are too theoretical (knowledge based), rather than experience based; they do not effectively educate students about everyday business skills, including sales, marketing, people management, administration, et cetera. He believes these skills are only learned practically.	Continuing onto the idea of real-world experience, A2 believes that the best way to teach entrepreneurship is through exposure. Students should work in start-ups and be provided with opportunities to interview entrepreneurs.
The Argument of Nature over Nurture	When asked about the extent to which they agree with the statement "entrepreneurs are born not made," Interviewee A1 states that anyone can become an entrepreneur if properly motivated, claiming that passion is important, as it allows one to stay disciplined and on track with one's objectives. He believes that this is the main reason why most people do not want to incur the pressure of running a company and would much rather be an employee.	A2 slightly agrees with the statement "entrepreneurs are born not made," as she believes that individuals can possess traits that facilitate entrepreneurship, though even without a natural fluency in said skills, an individual can adopt them, given that they possess the necessary learning attitude and mindset.

Image 7 - Interview Between Interviewee A1 & A2.

4.2.2 GROUP B

Entrepreneurs that began a venture or project after having graduated in entrepreneurship.

- Interviewee B1: Founder of Kaiyan Kwok
- Interviewee B2: Founder of Glow Play and Desensor

Interviewee	B1	B2
Academic Performance	Interviewee B1 claims to be an average student.	B2 claims to be an average student in both high school and university.
Interviewee	B1 states that they excelled at	B2 participated in several business case
Background	information technology (IT) and art; her passions.	competitions and gained extensive start-up experience in doing so.
Entrepreneurial Stimuli	B1 was driven by her passion for art and started a business.	B2 also chose to begin her first project, Glow Play, to make a positive impact on society. Her second project, Desensor' began after she spotted an opportunity to become a first mover in the Non-fungible Token. (NFT) space.
Nature of Business	B1 designs and sells merchandise based on the artistic designs that she creates.	Glow Play is a project that provides toys to children with special needs. 'Desensor' is a tool that facilitates the creation of Non-fungible Tokens (NFTs), a blockchain-based technology.
Impact of Study on Entrepreneurship	Having to study business in university had a negative effect on B1's progression towards becoming an entrepreneur. While studying, she was driven by her passion for art and started a business, however she did not have time to manage it, especially while preparing for exams, so she was unable to continue until after graduating. Though some may find theoretically taught business courses useful, B1 identifies as a practical-learner and saw that she was not getting as much value in university as she would have if she had started her own business; an important consideration for those who share the same personality type.	B2 states that while her education in the Thammasat School of Innovation did help in developing her analytical thinking abilities, it did not provide her with the technical knowledge required in day-to-day entrepreneurship: she gained a sizable portion of her skills through case competitions, first-hand research, and through making connections with investors and entrepreneurs which she meets at seminars.

Image 8.1 - - Interview Between Interviewee B1 & B2 (cont.).

<p>Source of Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition</p>	<p>B1 states that having a 'growth mindset' allowed her to develop her skills as an entrepreneur. When asked about entrepreneurial progression, she once again puts emphasis on practical learning; it is a way of learning that is continuous, it does not stop after graduation, and allows entrepreneurs to improve their skills outside of an educational environment. Entrepreneurs may not even need to gain additional knowledge, but can</p>	<p>B2 participated in several business case competitions and joined workshops related to social enterprises, start-ups, and marketing, which gave her a repertoire of entrepreneurial skills.</p>
<p>Beliefs on Effective Teaching of Entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Based on her experience in university, B1 puts emphasis on practical learning. She sees that an effective business course must allow students to play an active role in their education. Giving students the opportunity to take risks and act is vital in adopting an entrepreneurial mindset. B1 believes that internships and other real-world experiences would be greatly beneficial.</p>	<p>B2 states that hands-on team projects are important, as they can help students learn 'people skills,' important in running a business enterprise, including concepts such as delegation or trust.</p>
<p>Argument of Nature over Nurture</p>	<p>B1 partially agrees with the statement that 'entrepreneurs are born, not made' as certain personality types may facilitate entrepreneurship; some individuals may be natural hard workers, or perhaps find natural talent in risk taking. B1 also disagrees with the statement because she sees that those who are passionate enough, can put in the time, effort, and dedication to learn the skills others may possess naturally, and even surpass them; B1 has started two businesses so far through her passion, despite struggling with education.</p>	<p>B2 states that she does not come from a family with a business background but was motivated by her own visions and goals; anyone can follow this same path.</p>

Image 8.2 - Interview Between Interviewee B1 & B2.

4.2.3 GROUP C

Entrepreneurs that did not study entrepreneurship (dropout entrepreneurs).

- Interviewee C1: Founder of Classic Move Co., Ltd.

Interviewee	C1
Academic Performance	Interviewee C1 initially attained a GPA of 3.6, however after identifying that his course was not helping in the achievement of his entrepreneurial goals, he put less effort into his education, resulting in a 2.5 GPA shortly thereafter.
Interviewee Background	C1 initially studied at the Darunsikkhalai School for Innovative Learning (DSIL), a project-based learning school located in Bangkok. C1 then moved to the Global English School (GES) to complete grade 11. C1 comes from a family of entrepreneurs, where both his mother and father are businesspeople.
Entrepreneurial stimuli	Before grade 11, C1 worked at several cafes and quickly discovered that working a salary job was not what he wanted to do. C1 therefore, dropped out of school after grade 11 to start his venture and pursue his passion.
Nature of Business	C1 started Classic Move Co., Ltd., an institution that teaches coffee art and other skills used by baristas.
Impact of Study on Entrepreneurship	C1 believes that skills learned during his time in DSIL and GES are used on a day-to-day basis in entrepreneurship. C1 sees value in connections that one may gain from studying a business course with future potential entrepreneurs. However, C1 does not believe that education triggers one's interest in becoming an entrepreneur; instead, it is based on one's personal environment, stating that his family was a key driving factor in his pursuit of entrepreneurship. Due to the high value, he puts on networking and regular use of skills he learned in high school, C1 plans to study entrepreneurship in university once his business is self-sufficient.
Beliefs on Effective Teaching of Entrepreneurship	C1 believes that an effective course curriculum in entrepreneurship should be flexible and customizable. He also sees the benefits of project-based over theory-based learning and believes that this is also another vital aspect of an effective entrepreneurial course. C1 believes that a good entrepreneurial course should provide students with real-world experience through internship opportunities.
The Process of Entrepreneurial Development	C1 believes that sales are one of the most important skills he uses as an entrepreneur, which does not only include selling a project, but also oneself and one's ideas, a concept vital in succeeding as an entrepreneur. C1 also identifies communication as another important skill possessed by successful entrepreneurs.
The Argument of Nature Over Nurture	C1 fully agrees with the statement that "entrepreneurs are born, not made," claiming that while one may choose a different path early on in life, eventually they will be led into becoming an entrepreneur. He further elaborates, saying that those who are not born to be entrepreneurs may try pursuing entrepreneurship, but will fail. C1 concludes that passion is a core aspect of one's entrepreneurial spirit, allowing one to dedicate oneself to long-term goals, and continue through failure, essentially the 'make-or-break' of an entrepreneur (the beliefs of William Heinecke).

Image 9 - Interview Between Interviewee C1.

4.2.4 GROUP D

Control group: those who did not study entrepreneurship and are not entrepreneurs.

- Interviewee D1: Biomedical Science Student

Interviewee	D1
Academic Background	D1 decided to study biomedical science due to her passion and interest. D1 elaborates that studying biomedical science will allow her to expand to multiple career paths in the future.
Impact of not Studying Business Management	<p>D1 believes that having entrepreneurial skills would be beneficial for anyone in any career. She states that for her career path, financial and accounting skills could be useful for calculating projections relating to chemical substances.</p> <p>D1 currently lacks business knowledge and as a result, wishes to learn more about entrepreneurship. However, she thinks that if she took a business course, it wouldn't have altered her career path as she is passionate about biomedical science, not business management.</p> <p>D1 states that in the future, running her own business wouldn't be feasible as she lacks business knowledge and funding.</p>
Beliefs on Effective Teaching of Entrepreneurship	D1 believes that business courses only teach business theories which are inapplicable to real-world scenarios. She claims that the most effective way to master entrepreneurial skills is through gaining real-world experience.

Image 10 - Interview Between Interviewee D1.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS

4.3.1 ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AS A STIMULUS

In the interviews, none of the participants in Groups A and B claimed to be top performing students. Interviewee C1, who was initially a top performer, saw a decline in grades as he focused on tasks aligned with his entrepreneurial goals. Overall, academic performance has little influence on student entrepreneurship.

4.3.2 The Market Gap Stimulus

The identification of a market gap can play a role in fostering student entrepreneurs. Some interviewees in Group A started projects while studying, driven by market needs. Others in Group B pursued their passions after graduation. Interviewee C1 dropped out to capitalize on his barista skills. Although the market gap stimulus is a factor, its impact lacks quantitative evidence.

4.3.3 THE REAL-WORLD EXPERIENCE STIMULUS

Interviewees in Groups A and B gained real-world experience through various means, such as starting ventures or participating in case competitions. Interviewee C1 had experience as a barista. Real-world experience strongly correlates with student entrepreneurship.

4.3.4 STUDYING ENTREPRENEURSHIP VS FOSTERING STUDENT ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Studying entrepreneurship does not appear to be the main stimulus for student entrepreneurs. While some interviewees found benefits in their education, others felt it contributed little. Personal passion and family background are more influential in fostering student entrepreneurship.

4.3.5 The Family Background Stimulus

Family background plays a significant role in fostering student entrepreneurship. Studies and interviews highlight the impact of family support and the influence of entrepreneurial parents. However, passion remains a more significant stimulus than family background.

4.3.6 The Passion Stimulus

Passion is a driving force in fostering student entrepreneurs. The correlation between passion and entrepreneurial intent is strong. All sources emphasize the importance of passion as a stimulus, making it a crucial factor in student entrepreneurship.

4.3.7 The Argument of Nature Over Nurture

There is a debate between nature and nurture in student entrepreneurship. Some believe that entrepreneurs are born, while others argue that determination and the right mindset can lead anyone to become an entrepreneur. Passion is a core aspect of the enterprising spirit.

Considering the quantitative and qualitative data, passion plays a pivotal role in student entrepreneurship, deterring the argument of nature over nurture. While certain skills may facilitate entrepreneurship, becoming a student entrepreneur requires time, motivation, and effort.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the exploration findings, it is apparent that **student entrepreneurship can be fostered through three types of factors: minor, moderate, and major stimuli**. Because it was found that a student's academic performance is unlikely to affect their choice of becoming a student entrepreneur, it may be ruled out from all categories. Furthermore, because several factors from the mentioned categories have been proven to take effect on a student's decision to become an entrepreneur, the null hypothesis, "student entrepreneurship cannot be fostered through external stimuli, as entrepreneurs are born, not made," can be ruled out, as the exploration favors the idea that entrepreneurs can indeed be 'made' through a variety of different factors and choices.

The first category is, **minor stimuli**, which includes factors that only play a small role in a student's choice of becoming an entrepreneur, which may include the identification of a market gap, and are unlikely to outright determine whether a student becomes an entrepreneur or not but may affect the time at which they become entrepreneurs. **While it was initially believed that studying entrepreneurship was one of the main stimuli in fostering student entrepreneurship, both quantitative and qualitative findings imply that it is only a minor stimulus**; only facilitating student entrepreneurship, through the provision of skills and knowledge, rather than fostering it. In other words, **university courses may facilitate entrepreneurship, but do not create student entrepreneurs**. The simple hypothesis, "studying entrepreneurship has a strong positive correlation with the fostering of student entrepreneurs" may therefore be ruled out.

The next category is **moderate stimuli**, which has a considerable effect on the fostering of student

entrepreneurs. Due to the commonality of real-world experience shared across all interviews, there exists a clear correlation. **Students are more likely to be driven into becoming student entrepreneurs, given that they have sufficient experience.** Furthermore, a **student's family background was identified as another significant factor in fostering student entrepreneurs.**

While a student does not need to come from a family of businesspeople to be an entrepreneur, their family environment can drive student entrepreneurship through providing financial support or even business knowledge. AlmaLaurea's findings support this idea; many students' families are major reasons why they chose to become entrepreneurs. The alternative hypothesis, "student entrepreneurship is fostered through the personal backgrounds of a student rather than through studying entrepreneurship" is proven to a certain extent, however limited as it has been found that student entrepreneurship is fostered through numerous stimuli, not only based on their personal backgrounds.

The final aspect is **major stimuli**, which is the 'make-or-break' of a student entrepreneur, the main stimuli in fostering student entrepreneurship. All sources, qualitative and quantitative, support the idea that **passion is the most crucial factor**, as there is a proven positive correlation of over 32 percent from the EJBMR study. Furthermore, Poznań University identified that over 65 percent of students became student entrepreneurs as it was their passion to do so. Interviewee D1 chose not to pursue entrepreneurship to follow her passion in biomedical science, which still shows that the trend of passion is a key.

The decision-maker remains true for individuals who are not entrepreneurs. Interviewees from groups A, B, and C were either passionate about entrepreneurship itself, used entrepreneurship to pursue their passions, or a combination of both. The shared similarity across all sources of data shows the significance of passion in fostering student entrepreneurship, making it arguably the most important factor, thus proving the complex hypothesis: "a student's passion for entrepreneurship has a greater impact on their entrepreneurial intent than studying entrepreneurship." Further research should therefore be conducted in this area to determine the importance of passion for entrepreneurship compared to using entrepreneurship to pursue one's passion. Universities and other institutions may use these findings to design a course that allows students to pursue their passions, while providing sufficient knowledge, tools, and real-world experience.